

Muslim Students Association of the United States and Canada

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The Muslim Students Association of the United States and Canada (popularly known as MSA) is a network of Muslim communities that gather at and draw their support from college campuses. The history of the MSA dates back to the early sixties, a time period when Muslim migrants from the MENA (Middle East North Africa) region, South Asia, and Far East Asia migrated in large numbers to the United States in pursuit of graduate training in STEM fields and humanities. The earliest conventions of the MSA were held on college campuses in the Midwest region, including the University of Illinois campus in Champaign-Urbana. While majority of the MSA presidents were male graduate students, their wives played an even greater role in the growth of the Muslim Students Association by establishing the Women's Committee of the Muslim Students Association. One of the key ritual practices of the Muslim Students Association is the Quran Study Circle. It had been organized on college campuses such as Karachi University, Pakistan long before the pioneers of the Muslim Students Association migrated to the United States. Through discussing commentaries on the Quran collectively, students sought to upend the separation of religion from higher education that had been brought forth by colonization and elevate Islam as a methodological hook for an integrative model of learning. In the United States, the Quran Study Circle addressed the shared concerns of women around childrearing. Its participants were the pioneers of the Women's Committee of the MSA. They gathered at each other's homes and leveraged the Quran as a prompt for discussing shared experience of parenting and raising young Muslim children in suburban and ex-urban landscapes where there had been no existing institutional presence of Islam. These conversations inspired the growth of the North American Islamic School Movement. Examples include Al-Fatih Academy, a K-8th grade Islamic School that offers an integrative model of education with hopes of helping its student body learn to cognize their emotions. In addition to the development of Islamic schools, the Muslim Students Association also gave birth to the Islamic Society of North America (ISNA). Located in Plainfield, Indiana, ISNA seeks to elevate Islam and uplift Muslim-American communities through interfaith dialogue and civic engagement. One of the enduring hallmarks of the Muslim Students Association has been a distinctively feminine approach to activism centered around building relationships and cultivating emotional connection across religious, national, and racial lines of difference. MSA's commitment to a transnational ummah/community is best exemplified by the deep bonds of friendship and camaraderie between the movement's pioneers that endure to this day.

Date Range: 1960 CE - 2022 CE

Region: United States and Canada

Region tags: Canada

The United States during the Sixties and Seventies when higher education was expanding and the student population of large public universities swelling

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Nudrat Unus. Muslim Students Association of the United States and Canada: A Glimpse of the Seventies. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform
- Source 2: Nudrat Unus. Muslim Students Association of the United States and Canada: A Glimpse of the Sixties. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.npr.org/templates/story/story.php?storyId=6588450>
- Source 1 Description: The Girl in The Tangerine Scarf is a fictional account of the everyday life of the MSA community as experienced by a girl in a town on the southern outskirts of Indianapolis. It is written by Mohja Kahf who is the daughter of Mayssun Kahf, one of the founding members of the Women's Committee of the MSA.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: Talat Sultan. Islamization of Education: The Need and the Plan. Umm Al-Qura University Press
- Source 1 Description: It's a critique of secular models of education and a guide for action around a concept called Islamizing education.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Muslim Students Association routinely engaged in interfaith dialogue with other religious communities. These included members of the Nation of Islam and the Warith Deen Mohammad Community, predominantly African-American Muslims who had been living in urban centers such as Indianapolis, Chicago, and Gary, as well as American Catholics and their educational spaces such as the Notre Dame University in South Bend. Eboo Patel, a staunch proponent of pluralism and son of a former MSA member, recounts his father's spiritual growth as a graduate student at Notre Dame. The family would make routine trips to the school every year attending football games and paying homage to the statue of the Virgin Mary outside the chapel as a form of piety that trespasses doctrinal and institutional differences between Islam and Catholicism around a mutual respect for one another.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The religious affiliation of the MSA was fermented through everyday life on college campuses. The bonds of friendship among members of the MSA were forged through ongoing struggles around parenting and building a community without recourse to any institutional support. As such, they were more inclined to affiliate with one another based on emotion as opposed to a legal and impersonal system.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, proselytization (better known as Dawah) has been an enduring facet of the MSA. Many of the founding members of the MSA such as Talat Sultan, a former Islamic school principal and scholar of adolescent education, had been student activists in their homelands during the sixties. From that background, they learned ritual practices related to spreading Islam as a spiritual antidote to the divide between religion and science that had been a hallmark of western colonial education system in former British and French colonies in South Asia and MENA (Middle East North Africa). USA and Canada became the new frontier for this form of proselytization and it continues to this day with the designing of integrative educational curricula in private Islamic schools. The Islamic component is not the teaching of Islam per se as much as it is an approach to education as interdisciplinary and threads connected by an overarching compassion of God. This form of spreading Islam is not invested in legal reforms and does not rely upon the support of the state but rather seeks to mould the heart and transpired around the everyday life. This is what makes MSA such a key religious actor in contemporary US, especially in areas of adolescent education and parenting/motherhood.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: No, the MSA steers away from formal politics and engages in a far more radical form of politics that transpires around the everyday life of common people. Granted, there are political movements that have overlapping histories with the MSA namely the Muslim Brotherhood in Egypt and the Tablighi Jamaat in Pakistan, Bangladesh, and India. But the alliance between religion and politics transpires around the home with a sense of responsibility for improving the quality of life without reliance upon legal reform as best encapsulated by the Brotherhood's leadership around improving the livelihoods of fisherman in response to the environmental catastrophe precipitated by Gamal Nasser's construction of the Suez Canal. Scholarship on the Brotherhood's stewardship of the Suez Canal has been scarce because any consideration of the brotherhood as an environmental movement would disrupt the narrative that its a religious movement with a reactionary and backward politics while simultaneously call into question consensus forged by secular environmentalists around the benefits of dams.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: While the members of the MSA follow Islam, a religious tradition with a conception of apostasy, they do not rely upon any institution to punish someone who decides to abandon the community. In most cases, members drift and return to the community since ultimately its forged by familial ties and long lasting friendships. For instance, many children of the MSA pioneers were disenchanted by the insulated community in which they were raised but later grew up to admire the efforts their parents put towards developing a communities in places like Indiana where, except for African-American muslims who had formerly built institutions in urban centers such as Gary and Indianapolis, there were only silos and tractors. In the absence of any institutional support to rely upon, members of the MSA developed a slew of ritual practices to grow a sense of community including marriage ceremonies that were held inside the meeting rooms of tiny apartment buildings on the outskirts of Indianapolis and they were committed to one another much like the seventies youth who attended dance floors to feel fervor in otherwise declining and depressing urban areas and danced to the BeeGees Night Fever and showed "We Know How to Do It." MSA is very much an Islamic response to the fracture of institutional religion precipitated by the economic decline of the seventies and the beginning of deindustrialization. Building ties across differences of race, religion, and nationality was

what motivated them far more than accusing someone of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 2

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the MSA have Quran study circles, a ritual practice when they orally discuss commentaries on the Quran.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Angel Gabriel brought the scripture to Earth

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: However, it's hard to miss the building of the Islamic Society of North America (an extension of the MSA) as it stands tall in the flat and open fields of Plainfield, Indiana.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– No

Notes: The MSA conceives the heart as the site of the spirit that endures after the body dies. It

does so because the heart is considered to be the source of emotion and the cultivation of emotion is what the MSA seeks to do in order to realize its metaphysical goal of a pure ummah/community that transcends divisions of race and nationality. One of the significance of the heart over mind as the site of the spirit is the approach towards mental health. Al-Fatih Academy, an Islamic school started by Afeefa Syeed (daughter of MSA pioneer Syed Syeed) sees the role of education as one about helping adolescents cognize their emotions. The learning process is tactile, with students routinely encouraged to spend time in a sakena corner (a tranquility corner) that are designed within classrooms and also at their homes and touch tactile objects to calm down and regain their focus. This stands in stark contrast to normative clinical psychology which traces the source of the pathos to the immaterial mind as opposed to the material influences around the students such as digital technologies. While there is a growing consensus that digital technologies have a negative impact on mental health, Al-Fatih Academy does not condemn it all together and on the contrary demystifies it by organizing coding and programming sessions where students learn about the networks and communications that transpire behind the screen and in the process learn that they do not have complete control over the computer and instead the two shape each other's emotions.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: The MSA adhere to the Sunni tradition of Islam. But beyond theology, its religious practices are also shaped by broader shifts in science and technology over the course of the the 20th century which prioritized temperance and control over emotions for life in urbanizing areas around the world as exemplified by the display of grief at funerals. Sohaib Sultan, the son of Talat Sultan (a pioneer and early founders of the Muslim Students Association) passed away on April 16th 2021 leaving behind his post as the first Muslim chaplain at Princeton University, a young daughter, and a wife. But prior to his death, Suhaib was quite vocal about his impending death and the process whereby he overcame the fear of no longer being around his family and developing sukun/calm. He wanted his daughter to play around his grave rather than to sulk and feel despair. The importance of calm, lack of heightened

feelings, is conveyed by the materiality of the grave itself. it has a marble facade in the front with Sohaib's name and the rest is just a flat ground. I am attaching a picture of it here. Open the image with the voice of Sohaib talking about how he relinquished fear of dying and developed calm by opening this youtube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=whGqlaH9-Aw> Sohaib's testimony of overcoming fear of death and consequently approaching death as a mundane process of life resonates with the Nation of Islam, another 20th century Muslim tradition. If you ever observe a Nation of Islam funeral, you will rarely see anyone cry a lot or seem anguished and on the contrary everyone seems to treat the occasion of a funeral as a rite of passage that does not feel different/worse than your average day.

Reference: Hindu Life Program, Princeton University Living and Dying with Grace- with Sohaib Sultan and Vineet Chander

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: The Supreme God emanates feelings of compassion, also known as rahma, onto the people, thereby entering into a kinship with them around a shared emotion.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: In fact, the heart (also known as qulb) is the vessel that connects the supreme high god to you since it is the site of feeling.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: And considers your basic character to be good but always in need of discipline which makes it different than doctrine of original sin which sees you as born with a faulty character and at the behest of divine intervention.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: knowledge of time as eternal

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: But you may praise the natural wonders of the high god including stars.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: the genuflections in salat (prayer) are a way to communicate with the supreme god.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Salat, prayer, could be considered as a form of divination.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: A great example of a human spirit that guided the living is a young boy who was the son of one of the founder members of the MSA Women's Committee and passed away from burns after an arson set by KKK outside Indianapolis. The movement grew around women gathering in Quran study circles to discuss the shared challenges of parenting in the absence of institutional support and that effort was guided by the boy's spirit. I learned about the story after a chance encounter with one of the girls who was friends with the boy's sister and currently teaches Islam at a US college.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The reward of Bilal's spirit was the formation of the Muslim Students' Association and the North American Islamic School Movement.
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: The memory of the human spirit is alive. The dead shape the living as encapsulated by Bilal. While he was never referenced in any of my ethnographic interviews with the women pioneers of the MSA, their shared feelings of pain and love at raising children together was testament to the extent to which he continued to impact them even in his bodily absence.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

–Yes [specify]: Through Quran study circles, also known as Halaqa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: That physical sensation is felt through the feeling of compassion for other human beings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Time is understood as eternal with future and past unfolding simultaneously

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Knowledge of interplanetary life

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Compassion for instance

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: While the hungry supernatural is redolent in buddhist traditions prompting ritual practices of feeding the hungry ghosts, the Muslim supernatural does not feel hunger. That said, hunger itself is routinely understood as a state of death. The Navy Bean Soup, the staple dish of the Nation of Islam, for instance exemplifies a shift away from eating as a pleasure of the palate to a scientific method for maximizing nutrients and minimizing food intake that took place during the progressive era. One of the works of the food is that it evoked memories of enslaved ancestors who forgot they were Muslim (in other words spiritually dead) because they ate the food their masters fed them (food full of salt and excessive). The Muslim Students Association is not the Nation of Islam yet its members routinely talk about the large extent to which African American Muslims shaped the ways in which they learned to develop religious piety, a claim supported by evidence of collaboration between the two groups especially around adolescent education.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They feel compassion and that feeling flows to human beings through the practice of reproduction since compassion refers to both a type of emotion as well as the womb

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: However the two are intertwined and form a kinship around feelings of compassion. Compassion flows from Allah to his believers. It also refers to the womb, thus highlighting the connection between divinity and fertility

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Members of MSA held festive eating gatherings to celebrate occasions such as a marriage. The sites were ordinary and intimate such as the meeting room of an apartment building since the members lived in such abodes and had a very meager lifestyle as graduate students

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: The MSA grew in response to the lack of institutional spaces of religious gathering for Muslims. They established the Islamic Society of North America in Plainfield Indiana and started the establishment of private Islamic schools. The most important Religious spaces of gathering was the household where women members held quran study circle. While mosques are routinely considered a quintessential religious space for Muslims, most mosques in the US were constructed in the aftermath of 9/11. Before that, Islam was far less institutional and far more domestic.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The most sacred object is the Quran. Quran study sessions, also known as halaqa, facilitated women members to form relationships of sisterhood and trace their maternal responsibilities to a Divine compassion. Thus arose a deeply conservative form of Islamic feminism that overlapped and diverged from conservative feminism in other traditions such as white protestants during the sixties and seventies.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Yes. The supernatural expresses care by endowing the believer with feelings of compassion

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murder of anyone is a grave sin

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Members of MSA implemented meticulous chores related to home cleaning that centered around performing salat. The children learned to perform the chores from adults, with the girls shadowing the women and the boys shadowing the men. A disciplined lifestyle couched around piety intended to get rid of laziness.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Also known as sihr, sorcery is a form of beguilement and deception that concerns the supernatural in the Islamic tradition and for the members of the MSA. A great example of sorcery is shaitaan, the devil, and members of the MSA conceived it in relation to the secularization of the educational system in french and anglo colonies that effectively rendered religion as a sect which robbing spirituality from the study of the sciences. The United States with its expanding institutions of higher education inspired the pioneers of the MSA to spread Islam through education.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Respect for elders was a key fabric of the Muslim Students Association, valued highly to overcome divisions of race. The early history of the MSA is replete with seemingly ordinary stories of young children of migrants from South Asia and the Middle East learning about the black experience in the United States from the African-American adults in the community.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossiping is looked down upon since it generates ill will, also known as fitnah, but with the formation of a tight knit community gossip was also a key source of intimacy between members of the MSA.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Property crime is frowned upon. Members of the MSA were targeted for property crime with arson committed at the Islamic Society of North America estate in Plainfield, IN and of course the tragic murder of a young kid named Bilal after the young family's home was lit on fire. Members of the MSA rarely received any help from legal authorities which further cemented their belief in forming a community that doesn't require the law for its reproduction. It would emerge as a community anchored around the home and the school.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Yes. These rituals include salat (prayer) and halaqa (Quran study group). The desire for engaging in these ritual practices are enhanced by engaging in seemingly mundane and non-doctrinal activities such as managing home. For similar examples of Muslim women cultivating piety in a non-American context, see Saba Mahmood's *Politics of Piety* which is an ethnographic study of Islamic revival among contemporary Muslim women in Egypt.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The performance is key since it allows for the reproduction of the community. In the absence of any institution to offer recourse, members of the MSA adhered to the ritual practices strictly. The effect was intimacy among family members and a deep commitment to hard work since it took a lot of labor to build these tight-knit relationships between people who came to the United States and the ex-urban areas dotted with large public universities from different parts of the Muslim world and the inner city.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Dawah, an invitation to non-Muslims for considering conversion to Islam, was a key practice animating the work of the Muslim Students Association. Stories are replete of young families driving from a university in Colorado all the way to Indianapolis in order to engage in dawah.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, economic justice is highly valued by the members of the MSA. Afeefah Syeed, daughter of Syed Syeed who helped founded the MSA, is presently the principal of an Islamic school in northern virginia called al-Fatih Academy and designed the curricula to instill in the student body the virtue of making sure people are paid for their hard work. For instance the students helped pick up trash and clean the streets so that they can feel the Prophet's dictum that a worker should be paid long before he or she sweats.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the secular history of personal hygiene and the religious history of personal hygiene overlap in the formation of the Muslim Students Association. Members of the Muslim Students Association approach hygiene as a responsibility, stewardship, for the body. The best example is sex education at Al-Fatih Academy in Reston Virginia whose principal, Afeefah Syeed, is the daughter of one of MSA's pioneers. Sex ed routinely tends to create an antagonistic relationship between the individual and his or her body, with sexuality seen as a source of contagion, but al-fatih's approach facilitates the individual to sacralize their body.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: the punishment of the supernatural is not necessarily the effect of a certain cause. For instance, one of the worrisome phenomena for the pioneers of the Muslim Students Association is the diminishing value of womanhood and motherhood best encapsulated by a woman who lacks strong relationships with men and feels frustrated whenever a man slights her. The cause of that is not necessarily the man but rather an education system that devalues emotions and measures success through measurable standards.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Through institutions that are bereft of spirituality especially the education system

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Done to remind the practitioner that ritual-devotional adherence constitutes an entire way of life.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Notes: The MSA sought to challenge the existing group norms of higher education, especially the aura of specialization that came about due to the separation of the sciences from the humanities. They were resisting rather than enforcing groups norms but in so doing gave rise to an intimate communities which had its own normative practices as well.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: selfishness stems from specialization while the MSA sought to revive an interdisciplinary approach to education that instilled humility about the interconnectedness of life.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Members of the MSA created a feminine Islam which sees the divine as essentially good and kind. Such a force would not mete out punishment randomly, ala the Calvinist deity.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: while the concept of the afterlife, also referred to as akhira, is redolent in the Islamic tradition, there is a certain level of ambiguity to how the Islamic traditions that developed in the United States such as the Nation of Islam and the Muslim Students Association approach the concept. The Nation of Islam states openly that they see this life and the afterlife as interwoven and dimensions of reality that are experienced in the here and now rather than set apart by two separate times. While the MSA do not necessarily challenge the doctrine of the afterlife, they nonetheless focus on the here and now as well especially with regards to parenting and education. The piety for both movements was very much shaped and informed by changes in the seemingly non-religious/secular aspects of US and to a large extent global history including the formation of childhood, scientific reforms around hygiene, and greater investment in motherhood as a mechanism for reforming the city. While doctrinally afterlife is a meaningful theological category for the MSA, I would make a case for approaching the afterlife as the transformation that unfolds in this life and to therefore consider time as eternal and constantly in flux as opposed to linear and discrete.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Example includes colonization of the education system which separated the sciences from the humanities and robbed religion of its capacity to inform how we practice medicine for instance while reducing religion to a sect.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

Notes: Punishment consists of a mentality that sees religion as private while aspires for other fields of study for its practical application in worldly affairs.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the failure of local communities to resist against Anglo and French colonization is an example of punishment in this life meted out in the realm of the political.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: The sepoy rebellion and its quashing is an example of such a defeat

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, especially when one considers the extent to which public health issues in colonial south asia such as malaria were precipitated by the transcontinental expansion of agriculture, leaving farm communities in a state of famine while food products travelled long distances over the railroad. Medicine arose in response to such illnesses while religion was sidelined in debates around treatment.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: Yes, many pioneers of the Muslim Students Association engaged in religious piety to discover an explanation for the hardships and loss they endured on their migratory journeys. Talat Sultan, one of the founding members, has been greatly influenced by Maulana Abu Ala Maududi's speeches and writings on the need of a Muslim ummah/community and when asked why, he reminisced the sacrifices his parents made migrating from colonial India to the new born nation-state of Pakistan and argued Maududi helped him understand why that sacrifice was meaningful and not a waste. When Talat and his fellow graduate students who started the MSA moved to the United States, they wanted to figure out the reason behind the suffering they endured as racialized minorities with their homes and spaces of gathering routinely attacked. These are examples of punishments that bolstered their spirituality and

orientated them to the United States as a new frontier in their quest to Islamicize knowledge through reforms in adolescent education.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, illness is the earliest sign of living under colonial occupation and members of the MSA are acutely aware of that. Their piety is a response to and informed by scientific reforms around childhood and motherhood that took place at the turn of the twentieth century to mitigate the ill-effects of industrialization and urbanization.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the MSA aspire to cultivate the ethical virtue and feeling of compassion which also refers to the womb. The movements' pioneers are a group of women who held Quran study circles to talk about their shared experience of motherhood. They see reproduction as a gift from the supernatural and reminder that women receive their power from the supernatural rather than from men. Such a theological understanding of womanhood makes the MSA both a critique of seventies feminism while simultaneously its product.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: done through highly personal ways without a cause-effect principal. For instance, the reward for prayer is discipline and love for hardwork but it isn't measurable and rather produced through ephemeral feelings of compassion among family members.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Notes: But instead done to develop intimacy which can feel constraining but ultimately built around difference rather than sameness

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The rewards in this life I would argue are stressed more. Its an example of how feelings and mentality do not easily map onto doctrine.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The most important reward is a community knit together by feelings of compassion that flow from the supernatural.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - No
 - Notes: Members of the MSA engage in non-formal politics of building relationships and cultivating feelings as opposed to the formal politics of changing laws. There has been plenty of anti-Muslim literature that reference the threat of the MSA and its alleged affiliation with the Muslim Brotherhood but even they recognize that the power of the MSA lies in its ability to change society from within especially in the field of education. What they call a form of 'stench' Jihad is an approach to Islamizing the United States that unfolds around the day to day encounters in the home and the school.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: While the pioneers of the MSA were urban graduate students, they shared in common a disenchantment with the mechanization of time and relationships in the city. But rather than revert to an agrarian society, they sought to reproduce tight knit communities in urban areas. The process entails eating collectively so healthy crops are important to them. The novel, *Girl in a Tangerine Scarf*, by the daughter of one of MSA pioneers offers a thick description of the lawn behind a victorian home in southern outskirts of Indianapolis where the pioneers congregated and the mulberry trees that dotted the green landscape. The children were deeply enchanted by nature.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, migration is a shared experience for members of the MSA: migrating from the inner city and from cities in the middle-east and south asia to the ex-urban town in the United States. The Hijra, prophet's migration from Mecca to Medina, is a constitutive experience in the broader Islamic tradition as well.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: As noted previously, cultivating the feeling of compassion is a constitutive element of the piety for members of the MSA. Compassion also refers to the womb. Women members of the MSA played a leading role in the movement's growth and they used to hold quran study circles at each other's home discussing their shared experiences and struggles of raising young children in seventies America.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of an end times are redolent in the Islamic tradition. The MSA however sees the end times as the corrosion of the education system prompted by the separation of religion/spirituality from the school and seeks a revival around an integrated model of curricula that sees all the subjects taught as interconnected and linked to a divine purpose.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the community practices norms around dress, decorum, and discipline. It allowed for the growth of the community as well as leading some younger members to move away only to return with the key insight that the movement sought to build a community out of difference rather than regulate difference towards producing conformity. Many intellectual voices such as Eboo Patel who extol the virtue of religious pluralism as a deep seated mentality in American religious history are children of the MSA pioneers.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Notes: The conventions of the society lead people astray and unhappy while morals remind one of the importance of a spiritual growth in one's educational training and upbringing.

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Notes: the moral norms are explicitly linked to concrete physical concerns about the formation of a community in United States where during the sixties and seventies there were not many religious spaces for Muslims apart from the institutions that had been developed by black Muslim groups in cities over the course of the early 20th century. One of the key problems facing Muslims in the postwar period was the growing suburbanization of American religion, with the sunbelt region from Charlotte NC to Orange County California for instance dotted with large homogeneous housing units that were insulated from urban spaces. The midwest region gave birth to the Muslim Students Association, with the movement hosting an annual conference at large public universities such as University of Illinois Champaign Urbana and other

schools in southern Illinois, Indianapolis, Michigan, and Wisconsin. A spatial understanding of the MSA as an example of sixties midwest student activism does not preclude or undermine the importance of metaphysical concepts however. The MSA after all were deeply invested in the metaphysical concept of a pure ummah/community which transcended racial and national differences and they sought to achieve that through moral norms related to dress, hygiene, food, and prayer. Women played a leading role, hosting quran study sessions to discuss their shared concerns over raising young children. The ummah consequently hinged around a consensus around motherhood as a shared experience which is why Jamillah Karim observes in her book that mothers continue to play a key role building bridges between Muslims that over the years cracked up due to concerns over immigrant anti-black biases and related tensions over who gets to define what is Islam. The morality of the MSA was very pragmatic and concerned with day to day concerns of mothers who do not care too much about doctrine. It consequently offers a great case study for theorizing religion outside the paradigm of a denomination or institution and more as an emotion that binds people of different backgrounds who are presented with similar concerns related to reproduction and parenting in suburban spaces.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: The quest to Islamize knowledge through an integrated model of curriculum is linked to stewardship of the body, building good character, and preparing children to redress complex pressing issues such as global warming that require insights across disciplines. In many ways, the MSA is a reformist movement that cuts across religion and education, with women leading the charge and drawing upon their experiences of childbirth to redesign adolescent education.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

Notes: The MSA is not a movement that relies upon commands. It has a much more looser and feminine understanding of authority. Most of the MSA moral norms emerged out of quran study circles, a ritual practice that invited young mothers to talk about their experiences of raising children. Quranic verses generated dialogue.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Notes: Metaphysical concerns do matter to the MSA. Specifically, there is a

metaphysical concern about impurity in education that came about due to colonization but the process of purifying it took place in the here and now. Specifically, it took place in the midwest region of the United States which during the late sixties and early seventies was one of the most potent spaces for radical student activism and politics.

Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No, the Muslim Students Association extends an Islamic affirmation of sexuality and reproduction. The movement heavily invests in sexuality as a source of good and one without which it would be impossible to realize the metaphysical vision of a pure community. As is the case with other Muslims that hold a positive view of sexuality such as Mormonism for instance, the MSA also regulates sexuality and condemns sexual practices that impede the formation of a pure community. These include casual dating which pioneers of the MSA fear instill lack of confidence and self-worth in women and fill the void of emotional bonds between children and parents.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: The Muslim Students Association separates boys from girls to evade eventual problems such as drinking and sexism. Talat Sultan, one of the founding members of the MSA and a former president of the organization, bemoans the deleterious effect of intermingling between the genders on the growth of boys and girls. He argues that boys start to inherit virtues of a toxic masculinity that sees a girl's body as a prospective booty and girls alternatively become more vulnerable to sexual assault. He cited the example of Supreme Court Justice Kavanaugh who allegedly raped a woman during a party while in high school, with Talat inscribing his alcohol intake to his ungainly behavior. According to Talat Sultan, sexual assault is a sign of a society that does not sacralize sex and as a consequence suffers from a crisis of reproduction and fertility. He shared an anecdote about meeting a non-Muslim woman on the plane who shared with him that her daughter was dating an Iranian man and mocked at the promise of virginity in today's day and age. Virginity however is not necessarily just the void of sex but a mentality of building a family. The MSA's investment in family makes it an example of the mid-sixties religious conservatism in the United States, with Talat Sultan observing that even non-Muslims in the United States cared about the reproduction of the family until the sixties when there was a sharp decline. He cites the example of John D. Rockefeller who could not run for president because he was divorced while presidents today openly brag about adultery. This fervent attack on sexuality outside of marriage at one clashes with the feminist movement of the late sixties which affirmed women's right to work outside the household and without supervision of a male patriarchal figure in the shape of a husband while simultaneously adds a conservative layer to the era's feminist awakening by warning that the weakening of marriage would come at a steep cost and women would have to pay for it. In an era where fertility rates are low around the world at an unprecedented rate, the conservative

feminism of the sixties that MSA encapsulates is starting to gain increasing popularity as most millennial aged women are interested in stretching out their reproductive age and learning how they can have babies as opposed to fight for equal pay at work and right to work outside the domestic space of the household.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Food facilitates religious gathering and the Muslim Students Association is no exception. The community formed bonds of brotherhood and sisterhood around large dinner tables and outdoor eating festivals during its nascence and continues to do so with so many chapters of the MSA at colleges and universities organizing field trips to national parks and eating food collectively. Ramadhan, the month of fasting, is the most intense period of experiencing time in relation to eating and not-eating and it continues to inspire Muslim Students Association. The Islamic Society of North America, ISNA, an out post of the Muslim Students Association, established a "green ramadhan" initiative in 2014 with the goal of creating environmental awareness and reducing carbon footprints by changing the mindsets of mosques and islamic centers with regards to how they consume food.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Time is perhaps the most category of analysis in the study of the Muslim Students Association. Sacrificing time is a key feature of the movement's piety. Many of its pioneers such as Talat Sultan were greatly influenced by the speeches and writings of Maulana Abu Ala Maududi when they were young teenagers and observing the birth of Muslim nation-states such as Pakistan and Egypt that had been former British colonies. Maududi was inspirational because he offered a solution to a quandary that had plagued Muslims who had lived under British rule: do you invest in the new colonial education system and become a working professional at the expense of reneging religion or do you latch onto religious education at the expense of lacking opportunities to professionalize? These seemingly antithetical pathways shared in common an understanding of religion as a wholly separate domain of life, one excluded from preparation for the workplace. In the absence of religion, a new concept of time started to shape everyday life: mechanical time. Mechanical time was most visible in the designing of cities. Lyalpur, present-day Faisalabad, for instance has a marketplace and the top of the tallest building features a round shaped clock that rings a bell at the turn of every hour. Mechanical time conflicts with Islam: the former posits a progressivist notion of time that gradually progresses to an impending future with incremental improvement along the way while the latter sees future and past happening simultaneously and time itself as an absolute whole. Disenchanted by the erasure of religion from the educational system and its construction as a discrete social domain, Maududi gave speeches and wrote polemics that called upon the youth to elevate Islam as a methodology for remaking the entire educational system into one that integrates the various subjects, a practice that Talat Sultan refers to as Islamization of Knowledge. Long before he migrated to the

United States and helped start the Muslim Students Association, Talat Sultan engaged was busy Islamizing knowledge as an undergraduate student at Karachi University. He engaged in a series of ritual practices that collectively point to a heightened experience of time. As a member of the Islami Jamiat ul tulabah, the largest organization of Muslim students in Pakistan during the late fifties, Sultan would organize a seminar and then spread the word to 3-5 people and submit a report at the end of each month with details on how many people he contacted and how many books he distributed. The report also included the disciplinary practices the worker underwent: how many prayers he offered and on how many days he studied the Quran. To ensure workers were well-trained, the group established Islamic study circles. The study circle met twice per week. At one meeting, students would study the Quran and discuss its commentaries. The MSA would continue the tradition in the new milieu of midwest United States. In many ways, this intense and self-reflective experience of time mimics the processual time that was instituted by English colonial educational system since the worker is always changing and training and improving. But in this case, religion orders the processual experience of time.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 6

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 30

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 10

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Islamic Society of North America, an outpost of the Muslim Students Association, raises funds for famine relief through collaborating with institutions such as the Center for Interfaith Action on Global Poverty. Interfaith has been a hallmark of Muslim Students Association's activism since the organization's inception in the early sixties. The method is animated by a conviction that political problems arise out of lack of relationships and that there is no more potent force at bridging divisions than religion. Through building relationships with other religious organizations around common problems such as global poverty, the MSA aspires to demonstrate that a change in heart can solve seemingly impersonal and abstract problems and to also offer a subtle critique of progressivism and its assumption that large scale reform is only possible through the law and from law makers.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Members of the MSA and Muslim-Americans more broadly seek non-institutional approaches to elderly care. The suspicion of institutional elderly care comes from observing non-Muslim families and fear that the institution would undercut the responsibility for care bestowed onto the young.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, there are numerous institutions in the United States that provide elderly care with funding from medicaid. But Muslims and immigrants at large aspire to care for their elders at home. There is a need for increased collaboration among Muslims and develop social gatherings since so many elderly lack friendship networks and find life inside the home far too claustrophobic and boring.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Muslim Students Association spearheaded the development of the North American Islamic School Movement. These private Islamic schools are accredited. Some are K-8th grade while others are K-12. They are located both in cities and suburbs and all around the United States. But not all Islamic schools are the same. Al-Fatih Academy, a school that was established by Afeefay Syeed (the daughter of MSA pioneer Syed Syeed) argues that while many Islamic schools tend to merely add the

subject Islam and Arabic to the core curricula, Al-Fatih is an experiment in designing an integrative model of curriculum. As such, it is a new model of adolescent education that happens to teach Muslim students as opposed to an Islamic school which is befitting since MSA itself was an educational reform that happened to have been started by Muslims graduate students.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, principals and teachers of the North American Islamic School system do not see public schools as a threat. In fact, many will encourage parents to send their children to a public school if the Islamic school lacks finances to hire counsellors or offer other basic needs.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, they interact with interfaith groups and research groups such as the Berkley Center.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: No, but it does encourage participants to give charity/zakat especially for making education more accessible. A great example is the Ikram Foundation, a non-profit operated exclusively by women, that provides educational funds for divorced women. They hold luncheons and exhort attendees to give money for the betterment in the lives of such women.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The IRS.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As little as possible. Members of the MSA are suspicious of police protection since they have been targeted by hate crimes in the past and discovered the legal system did not help.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Islamic Society of North America (ISNA) an extension of the MSA, hires lawyers to represent Muslim communities especially to fight against cities that bar from constructing a mosque.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Members can but as a group they are not necessarily required or encouraged to.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: luncheons, banquets, house gatherings, takeouts from restaurants, barbeque at national parks.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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